

AN INVESTIGATION ON STABILITY OF Y_2O_3 AND SINTERING BEHAVIOR OF FE-BASE ODS PARTICLES PREPARED BY HIGH ENERGY BALL MILLING

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Abstract

Fe based ODS powders were produced by high energy ball milling, followed by spark plasma sintering (SPS) for consolidation. The mixed powders of 84Fe-14Cr-2Y₂O₃ (Wt%) were mechanically milled for 10 and 90mins, and then consolidated at different temperatures (900~1100 °C). Mechanically-Alloyed (MAed) particles were studied by means of cross-sectional images using Scanning Electron microscopy (SEM). Both mechanical alloying and sintering behaviors were investigated by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HR-TEM). To confirm thermal behaviors of Y₂O₃, replica method was utilized after SPS process. After 10 minute, MAed powders analyzed by SEM show that a lamella structure consists of Fe and Cr rich region. After 90 minute, both regions were fully alloyed. The results of sintering behavior clearly indicated that as the SPS temperature increases, micro-sized defects were decreased and the density of consolidated ODS alloys was increased. TEM images revealed that precipitates smaller than 50nm in size appeared and they were proved to be YCrO₃.

1 Introduction

Mechanically-alloyed oxide dispersion strengthened (MA ODS) alloys exhibit high strength and outstanding creep property owing to the existence of fine grains and dispersed fine oxide particles. To obtain this specific property, pre-alloyed metal and Y₂O₃ powders are usually ball milled and then

thermo-mechanical treatments are applied [1]. Yttria (Y₂O₃) is widely utilized as an oxide for reinforcement, because it has thermo-dynamical and chemical stability. For that reason, ODS alloys are promising materials for nuclear applications. Among them, ferritic alloys have more radiation resistance than austenitic alloys due to the ferritic microstructure at elevated temperature around 973K [2-4], and therefore many previous experiments have been focused on modifying chemical compositions and preparation method for finely dispersed oxide particles [5-7].

In this work, to confirm clearly the behaviors of Y₂O₃, simplified Fe-14Cr-2Y₂O₃ ODS ferritic alloy was produced by mechanical alloying (MA) and spark plasma sintering (SPS) method for an investigation on stability of Y₂O₃ and sintering behavior of Fe based ODS particles.

2 Experimental procedure

Chemical composition of starting particles used in this work was 84Fe-14Cr-2Y₂O₃ (Wt%). All of them were pure more than 99.9% and their average size was from 40 to 50µm. Mechanical alloying of Fe, Cr and Y₂O₃ particles was performed by high energy ball mill machine (home made, P-300) under an Ar (high purity) atmosphere for various milling time (10-90mins). The bowl which contained Fe based powder mixture (10g) and the stainless steel balls of 8mm diameter (200g) was rotated at a speed of 850 rpm and the weight ratio of the balls to the powders was set at 20:1. After mechanical alloying, the two types of powders milled for 10 and 90min were

consolidated by means of spark plasma sintering at 900, 1000 and 1100°C for 30min. The SPS holding time was fixed in all conditions.

The MAed powders and sintered ODS alloys were analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD, Rigaku D/MAX 2500H) using Cu K α radiation operating at 40kV and 100mA. To confirm the behavior of mechanical alloying, the cross section of Fe based powders was characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, FEI Sirion). The sintering behaviors were analyzed by optical microscope (OM, Olympus) and the relative density was calculated by means of the Archimedes method. The observation of oxide particles was performed using high resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM, JEOL JEM-2100F) with EDS. The TEM samples were prepared using conventional electro-polishing method and replica method [3,8-9]. Extraction replicas can give us more coherent information about oxide analysis without matrix.

3 Results and discussion

3-1 Mechanical alloying

Generally, a ball milling has an effect on pre-alloying, size reduction and uniform distribution of powder materials. In the present work, it was adopted as first means of finely dispersing oxide particles in sintered alloys. The resulting cross-sectional images of MAed ODS powders prepared for 10 and 90min are presented in Fig. 1. In case of the MAed powder for 10min (MA10), a lamellar structure consisted of bright Fe rich region and relatively dark Cr rich one was observed because mechanical alloying was not finished yet. On the other hand, in case of MAed powder for 90min (MA90), it was hard to distinguish one region from the other and to find out Y₂O₃ particles in the matrix. In the preliminary results using our high energy ball mill machine [10], Fe based powder were fully homogenized and the value of lattice parameter of Fe was saturated after milling for 40 min. Eventually, compared to the previous experiments [11-13], high energy ball milling method was able to significantly reduce the MA times.

3-2 Sintering behavior

As a part of investigation the sintering behaviors, optical images to identify the characteristics of

consolidated ODS alloys using SPS method with various temperatures, as shown in Fig. 2. In case of sintering temperature at 900°C, many faults and pores were observed, while as rising temperature, they were decreased. Micro-sized defects in the sintered specimen at 1100°C were not shown and sound structures were obtained.

Fig.1. SEM images of Fe based powders with different mechanical milling time: (a) 10min, (b) 90min.

Fig.2. OM images of ODS alloys with various consolidation temperatures at (a) 900°C (MA90), (b) 1000°C (MA90), (c) 1100°C (MA90), and (d) 1100°C (MA10).

The results of calculated relative density about sintered specimens, as shown in Fig.3, help to support above OM image analysis. The initial relative density was less than 80%. As sintering temperature rises, the value of relative density increased dramatically. However, it had no significant influence on the relative density with MA time. The final value of relative density after sintering at 1100°C was similar to the theoretical density. As a result, it is found that the SPS

temperature for dense bulk must be set to more than 1100 °C in the fixed holding time of 30min.

Fig.3. Relative density of ODS alloys with various MA and SPS conditions.

3-3 Phase transition of Y_2O_3

XRD results of all MAed powders (red and black line in Fig.4.) revealed that the Y_2O_3 peaks were not detected anymore. It was reported that with increasing mechanical alloying time the magnitude of these peaks decreases and their width increases, due to a reduction in the crystallite size and to an increase in the deformation amount of the particles [14]. After SPS treatment (blue and green line in Fig.4), many uncertain peaks and $YCrO_3$ peaks with orthorhombic structure appeared. From the different XRD patterns between MAed powders and consolidated alloys it is probably deduced that Y_2O_3 particles would be decomposed during the MA process and then reformed to $YCrO_3$ through the SPS process.

Fig.4. XRD patterns of MAed powders and ODS alloys after SPS with various conditions.

Fig.5. TEM images of Fe based ODS alloy after sintering at 1100 °C: (a) specimen sintered by using MA90, (b) HREM image of $YCrO_3$ obtained by replica method, specimen sintered by using MA90 and (c) specimen sintered by using MA10.

For more detailed confirmation about $YCrO_3$ phase, the results of TEM analysis were illustrated in Fig. 5. In the first TEM image of Fig. 5(a) prepared using electro-polishing method, a number of oxide precipitates were observed. Their size was measured to be smaller than 50nm. The second TEM image of the consolidated specimen by SPS, as shown in Fig. 5(b), was prepared using replica method. The spherical oxide precipitate has been identified as $YCrO_3$ with orthorhombic structure. This result was consistent with the XRD one. On the other hand, consolidated specimen from MA10, similar to a lamellar layer of the previous MA process, long arranged coarse oxide clusters ($< 20\mu m$) which consist of Y-Cr-O was presented in Fig. 5(c). And it should be acted as a defect.

4 Conclusions

The aims of present work is to figure out the effect of various MA time and SPS temperatures on stability of Y_2O_3 and sintering behavior. From the experiment results, it is concluded that the MA time did not affect sintering behavior of Fe based ODS alloys, but only caused by SPS temperature. On the other hand, oxide behaviors were strongly influenced by the MA time. The best condition for the production of sound Fe based ODS alloys in this

work was the SPS temperature at 1100°C and the MA time in 90min.

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